

A Grand Master of Discrete Mathematics

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There are few Romanian mathematicians (computer scientists) having seven books published by important international publishers. Professor Sergiu Rudeanu is one of them. He has several titles published by Springer, North-Holland, World Scientific, Dunod (Paris), Kogaku Tosho (Tokyo) and Bentham (eBooks). As well as several others books printed by well-known Romanian publishers. Their titles reflect properly the fields in which Professor Sergiu Rudeanu was active for more than 50 years: Boolean and pseudo-Boolean methods in operations research, Boolean and lattice functions and equations, Lukasiewicz-Moisil algebras, ordered structures.

1. Pseudo-Boolean Methods for Bivalent Programming. Lecture Notes in Mathematics vol.23, Springer-Verlag, Berlin/Heidelberg/New-York 1966 (with Peter Hammer).
2. Boolean Methods in Operations Research and Related Areas. Springer-Verlag, Berlin/ Heidelberg/New-York 1968; also Dunod, Paris 1970 (with Peter Hammer).
3. Boolean Functions and Equations. North-Holland, Amsterdam/London 1974; also Kogaku Tosho, Tokyo, 1984.
4. Lukasiewicz-Moisil Algebras. Annals of Discrete Mathematics vol.49, North-Holland, Amsterdam/New-York/London 1991 (with V.Boicescu, A.Filipoiu, G.Georgescu).
5. Lattice Functions and Equations. Springer, London 2001.
6. Axioms for Lattices and Boolean Algebras. World Scientific, Singapore 2008 (with R. Padmanabhan).
7. Sets and Ordered Structures. Bentham eBooks, Oak Park, 2012.

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Looking to these titles, it is easy to note the passion for discrete mathematics (in particular Boolean structures) coming from his PhD supervisor Grigore C. Moisil, an important Romanian mathematician still representing a scientific and cultural icon 40 years after his death.

Grigore Moisil started his academic life in 1931 at A.I.Cuza University of Iași where he remained for almost 10 years before becoming a professor at the University of Bucharest. During these years, he taught the first modern algebra course in Romania (named “Logic and theory of proof”), and started writing papers based on the work of Lukasiewicz on multi-valued logic.

Somehow similarly, Sergiu Rudeanu was born in Iași on 9th February 1935, and moved then to become a professor at the University of Bucharest. This issue of the *Scientific Annals of Computer Science* (at University of Iași) celebrates scientifically the anniversary of his 80th birthday. It contains papers submitted by some of his (scientific) friends including George Georgescu (another important member of the Moisil’s school), certain PhD students of Sergiu Rudeanu: Dan Simovici, Afrodita Iorgulescu and Ioana Leuștean, some faculty colleagues and former students at the University of Bucharest: Cezar Câmpeanu, Daniela Cheptea, Denisa Diaconescu, Gabriel Istrate and Claudia Mureșan. We warmly thank all of them for contributing to this issue. Their papers were carefully reviewed by the members of the editorial board and some external reviewers. Many thanks to all of them for their high-quality reviews. Many thanks also to Sorin Iftene for his hard work of editing the papers, as well as to Andreea Stanciu for her work of posting the issue on our journal website.

This issue intend to present some features of Professor Sergiu Rudeanu: scrupulous rigour, importance of details, clear presentation. On the other hand, there are other aspects of Professor Rudeanu we would like to mention: hard worker, benevolence, calmness and harmony. It is not difficult to note his happiness and joy when hearing/learning an interesting idea (he has a specific smile for these situations). His light side is aligned with positive emotions in himself and around. The impression is that he is living and moving in his own universe, favouring a calm and emotionless interaction, a polite and tolerant behaviour. According to all these aspects, Professor Sergiu Rudeanu looks like a representative of the golden age of mathematics in mid 20th century. A discreet grand master of discrete mathematics.